

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The role of training, work discipline, workload, and emotional intelligence on the performance

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine and explain the effect of training, work discipline, workload, and emotional intelligence on performance Personnel The Ditreskrimus of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police is good simultaneously or partially. The paradigm of this study is positivist with approach quantitative. Collection data conducted in a manner cross-section by using a one-line questionnaire. The population in this research sample is all personnel Ditreskrimus of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police as many as 122 people were then sampled using the slovin formula and produced a sample of 55 people. The analytical tool used is multiple linear regression analysis. The results of the study show that training, work discipline, workload, and emotional intelligence simultaneously have a significant effect on performance Personnel Ditreskrimus Polda Southeast Sulawesi. Furthermore, the results of partial testing of training proved to be influential positive and significant to performance Personnel Ditreskrimus Polda Southeast Sulawesi. Work discipline positive and significant effect on performance Personnel Ditreskrimus Polda Southeast Sulawesi. Workload negative and significant effect on performance Personnel Ditreskrimus Polda Southeast Sulawesi. Furthermore, emotional intelligence is proven to have a positive and significant effect on performance Personnel Ditreskrimus Polda Southeast Sulawesi.

Keywords: Training; Work Discipline; Workload; Emotional Intelligence; Personnel Performance

1 Introduction

In various fields, especially organizational life, the human factor is the main problem in every activity in it. Organization is a system of formal, structured and coordinated association of a group of people who work together to achieve certain goals. An organization or institution, both government and private, requires the existence of potential human resource factors, both leaders and employees, in the pattern of tasks and supervision which is a determinant of achieving the goals of an organization or agency, both government and private. The aim of the police force is to realize domestic security which includes maintaining public order and security, orderly and upholding the law, providing protection, protection and service to the community and fostering public peace by upholding human rights. The performance of the Ditreskrimus Polda Sultra Regional Police is required to have good work capacity and work performance in order to carry out government duties and community services as well as possible because leaders and personnel are required to be able to formulate strategic policies

Training is an important HR development activity with various implication, especially in development HR in a manner whole. Activity training in a manner actual could involve organization for adapt, compete, excel, innovate, produce, secure, improve services, and achieve goals by (1). Therefore training is a learning process involving personnel so that skill acquisition, adoption rule and formation attitude (2). Following (2) stated that organizations that invest more in training Employees will achieve high performance and innovation. Organizational expenses for Internal training is an

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interpersonal and organizational learning practice on turn could increase performance and innovative employee. Based on the research findings of (3), (4), (5), (6) in their research findings show that training has a positive and significant effect on performance, meaning that an increase in training significantly improves performance.

Work discipline in the organization expects employees to work in accordance with what has been set by management (preventive discipline). Discipline will be emphasized more if employees experience unexpected violations and are not in accordance with predetermined standards. Research findings by (7), (8), (9), (10), (11) in their research findings show that work discipline has a positive and significant effect on performance, meaning that the higher the level of discipline of members in an organization, the performance will increase,

By (12), workload analysis is to identify both the number of employees and the qualifications of employees needed to achieve organizational goals. (13), workload analysis is the process of determining the number of working hours of people used or needed to complete a job within a certain time, or in other words workload analysis aims to determine how many personnel and how much responsibility or burden appropriate work delegated to an officer. By (14), workload is the volume of work results or records of work results which can show the volume produced by a number of employees in a particular section. Following (15), workload refers to the intensity of a person's work assignments. This is an opportunity to learn and grow rapidly. Based on the research results of (16), (17), (18), (19), (20), and (11) in their research findings show that workload has a positive and significant effect on performance,

By (21) perception of one's emotional intelligence is an interesting individual difference variable. For example, it might take into account a person's motivation for achieving emotional competence and a person's preference for acting on this competency. Also, individuals may be more likely to modify their behavior based on their beliefs about their abilities than their actual abilities. By (22) emotional intelligence is the ability to recognize our own feelings and the feelings of others, the ability to motivate ourselves, and the ability to manage emotions well in oneself in relationships with others. These abilities are different from each other and complement pure academic abilities, namely pure cognitive abilities as measured by IQ. Based on the research results of (23), (3), (24), (25), (26), (11), (6) shows that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on performance, meaning that the better the level of emotional intelligence, the better performance will be.

2 Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1 Training

Training that is process learning which in implementation in a manner systematically in order to change the behavior of trainees to achieve organizational goals by (27). This means that training is a learning process involve employee so that increase Skills which implementation outside education system with a short time through methods that emphasize application no theory.. Consistent with (28) opinion, training is part of the process training or non-formal education carried out by employees with the aim of so that increase Skills special for every employee. Next development ie skills improvement employee with follow training in effort increase performance work.

Following (29) put forward Training is a learning experience designed to achieve change relatively permanent in individuals who wish to improve their performance and ability to To do profession. Next Opinion which same by (30) explains that training refers to operational processes for teaching employees in a manner technical so that To do profession assigned. Next development ie skills improvement employee with follow training in effort increase performance work . Training is series activity which designed so that increase Skills, knowledge, experience or change attitude. With thereby in studies training intended process learning which involve Personnel so that improve that skill outside implementation system education with time which short through method which emphasize on application no theory. The description of the measurement of training variables, namely: (1) goals and targets/targets training, (2) participant training, (3) Theory training, (4) method training, (5) instructor, the measurement of the training variables was adopted from that opinion put forward by (31), (32), (27), (33), and research results (34), (35), (36).

2.2 Work Discipline

Discipline is a form of employee self-control and regular implementation and shows the level of seriousness of the work team within an organization, disciplinary action is used by organizations to provide sanctions for violations of work rules or of expectations. Complaints are used by employees who feel their rights have been violated by the organization. In other words, work discipline in employees is needed, because what is the goal of the organization will be difficult to achieve if there is no work discipline. In this study, as a support for the definition of work discipline, research personnel adopt various definitions of discipline, among them (37), discipline as management action to enforce organizational standards (discipline is management action to enforce organization standards).

By (38) the organization benefits from developing and implementing effective disciplinary policies. Without a healthy state of discipline, an organization's effectiveness may be severely limited. Furthermore, they say that effective disciplinary action will encourage the individual to increase performance which benefits the individual and thus the individual organization. According to (39) discipline is a form of training that enforces company rules. Discipline is not formed in an instant, but it takes coaching, continuous forging from an early age. Forging does not have to take precedence over violence, but firmness is needed, because firmness and firmness in implementing regulations is the main capital and absolute requirement for realizing discipline (40). Good work discipline reflects the magnitude of a person's sense of responsibility towards the tasks assigned to him. The better the employee's work discipline, it is expected that the higher the work performance achieved. Because work discipline is compliance and conscious adherence to the rules and conditions of doing work as well as working relationships and conditions. Work discipline is a person's behavior according to regulations, and work procedures or existing discipline are attitudes, behaviors, and actions regulated by organizational regulations, both written and unwritten. The indicators for measuring discipline used in this study are according to (11) work discipline consisting of dimensions or indicators, attendance, obedience, high level of vigilance, and ethical work..

2.3 Work load

By (12), workload analysis is to identify both the number of employees and the qualifications of employees needed to achieve organizational goals. Following (13), workload analysis is the process of determining the number of working hours of people used or needed to complete a job within a certain time, or in other words workload analysis aims to determine how many personnel and how much responsibility or burden appropriate work delegated to an officer. Seng & Yu (2005:1098) workload is the amount of work assigned or performed by a worker or unit of workers in a certain period of time. Workload is best described by analyzing the amount of work, the rate at which jobs are created, and the characteristics, distribution, and content of jobs. (15), workload refers to the intensity of a person's work assignments. This is an opportunity to learn and grow rapidly.

By (41), workload is a number of jobs that must be done by employees during a certain period of time. For example distinguishing between perceived workload and workload objectively. According to (42) defines workload as the amount of work a person must complete within a certain period of time. (43), workload is interconnected with many psychological problems; fatigue is one of them. The workload aspect seems to fall into three broad categories: amount of work and number of things to do; time and certain aspects of time to be considered; and psychological experience that is subjective in nature experienced by humans and workload is a mental construct that reflects the interaction of mental demands imposed on someone for the tasks they perform. (44), workload is the amount of work that must be done by someone at a certain time with a certain quality. Moreover, according to (45), workload can be defined as the amount of work that must be done by an individual. Workload is the extent to which an individual worker's capacity is needed to complete the tasks assigned to him, which can be indicated by the amount of work that must be done by the worker, and the time limit / time that the worker has to complete it. duties, as well as individual subjective views regarding workload. the work given to him. The indicators or dimensions of workload consist of targets, working conditions, and works standards (46), (47), and (11).

2.4 Emotional Intelligence

The emerging field of emotional intelligence has been enriched by the contributions of experts from various fields such as psychology, human resource management, and others who have produced various terminologies that include social intelligence (48), personal intelligence (49), emotional intelligence (50); (51), emotional literacy (52). Emotional intelligence involves the capacity to understand emotions, assimilate thoughts related to emotions, understand the information that emotions can provide to oneself, and manage emotions effectively (50). EI can be assessed most directly by asking a person to solve an emotional problem; for example, one type of emotional problem might involve identifying emotions in human faces, abstract designs, or color swatches (50). By (22) emotional intelligence determines the potential for learning skills based on five aspects: self-awareness, motivation, self-regulation, empathy and skills in developing relationships with others.

By (11) emotional intelligence refers to the ability to recognize our feelings and those of others, the ability to motivate ourselves and in relationships with others. The ability to monitor and control one's own feelings and those of others, and to use those feelings to guide one's thoughts and actions, is an important part of emotional intelligence itself. Dimensions or indicators of emotional intelligence consist of self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and skills in building relationships (53) and (11).

2.5 Personnel Performance

Institutional performance as within the scope of the Southeast Sulawesi Polda Ditreskrimsus Personnel organization is the result of the vision, mission and goals set within the organization. Institutional or organizational performance has been defined in the main tasks and functions of the organization. The main tasks and functions of the organization in organizational theory are detailed in a number of roles carried out by organizational personnel. By (54), Performance is the degree to which employees achieve job requirements efficiently and effectively. (55) Performance is a record of the results produced (produced) for certain job functions or activities during a certain period. The definition of performance as a result is also related to productivity and effectiveness.

By (56), performance is a measure that includes effectiveness and efficiency. Effective relates to achieving targets, while efficient is the ratio between effective output and input needed to achieve goals. (57) performance is real behavior displayed by everyone as work performance produced by employees according to their role in the company. Employee performance is a very important thing in the company's efforts to achieve its goals. (58) performance (work achievement) is the actual performance of employees compared to the expected performance. Employee performance is a comparison between actual work results and established work standards.

By (59) performance is the result of the work achieved by each INP member in the functional unit/regional unit in accordance with the general factors and specific factors. The performance of a personnel can be said to be good if it meets nine criteria, namely service orientation, communication, emotional control, integrity, empathy, commitment to the organization, initiative, discipline, and cooperation.

From the literature review. The conceptual framework of this study is shown below:

Figure 1 Research Conceptual Framework

The hypothesis is a temporary allegation of a relationship, cause and effect of variable performance that needs to be proven true. Based on the research framework, the hypotheses proposed in this study are as follows:

- Training, work discipline, workload, and emotional intelligence simultaneously have a significant effect on personnel performance
- Training has a positive and significant effect on personnel performance
- Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on personnel performance
- Workload has a positive and significant effect on personnel performance
- Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on performance

3 Methods

The design of this study is intended to provide an explanation of the causal relationship between variables through hypothesis testing, thus the research approach is verification and explanation (*explanatory research*). The population in this study were all 122 personnel of the Directorate of Special Criminal Investigation of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police. The scale of data measurement in this study uses a Likert scale. This study used data analysis methods consisting of two groups, namely descriptive statistical analysis and inferential statistical analysis. The purpose of using descriptive analysis in research is to provide an empirical description of the choice of statements and the frequency

distribution of respondents from the data that has been collected. The statistical analysis tool used in this study is multiple linear regression analysis, which is processed using SPSS 24 statistical *software*.

4 Results

4.1 Characteristics of Respondents

The description of the characteristics of the respondents in this study aims to explain the characteristics of the personnel Ditreskrimsub Polda Sultra which includes gender, age, years of service, rank/position, and last education which is shown in table 1 below:

Table 1 Characteristics of Respondents

No.	Characteristics of Respondents		Frequency (person)	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Man	44	80.0
		Female	11	20.0
		Total	55	100.0
2	Age (Years)	20-30	14	25.5
		31-40	25	45.5
		41-50	16	29,1
		Total	55	100.0
3	Working time (years)	1-10	16	29,1
		11-20	25	45.5
		21-30	14	25.5
		Total	55	100.0
4	Rank/position	BRIGADIER	4	7,3
		BRIPDA	4	7,3
		BRIGADIER	10	18,2
		POLICE BRIG	1	1,8
		BRIPKA	7	12,7
		AIPDA	14	25.5
		AIPTU	4	7,3
		IPDA	7	12,7
		IPTU	4	7,3
		Total	55	100.0
5	Last education	SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	11	20.0
		S1	37	67,3
		S2	7	12,7
		Total	55	100.0

Source: Primary primary data, 2022

4.1 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The results of the multiple linear regression analysis are presented in table 2, which are as follows:

Table 2 Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Influence Between Variables	Standardize d Coefficient	t- value	Sig. t	Results
Training → Personnel Performance	0.315	4.031	0.000	Received
Work Discipline → Personnel Performance	0.123	2.118	0.039	Received
Workload → Personnel Performance	-0.120	-2.141	0.037	Rejected
Emotional intelligence → Personnel Performance	0.670	7.689	0.000	Received
R : 0.966	F-value : 177.038			
R square : 0.934	sign. F : 0.000			
	n : 55			

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Based on table 2 above the results of multiple linear regression analysis, the regression analysis equation is obtained as follows:

$$Y = 0.315 X_1 + 0.123 X_2 + -0.120X_3 + 0.670X_4$$

Based on the results of the multiple linear regression analysis presented in the equation above, it can be interpreted that the R value of 0.966 indicates that the correlation between the independent variables namely training, work discipline, workload, and emotional intelligence on the dependent variable, namely personnel performance is strong.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.934 indicates that the diversity of training, work discipline, workload, and emotional intelligence variables on personnel performance can be explained by a model of 93.4 percent so that this research model has good model accuracy, because the numbers the coefficient of determination is getting closer to number one.

4.2 Hypothesis test

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis in table 2 above, it shows that simultaneously and partially training, work discipline, workload, and emotional intelligence significant effect on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Sultra which is described as follows:

4.2.1 Training, Work Discipline, Workload, And Emotional Intelligence Simultaneously Have a Significant Influence on Personnel Performance

Based on the simultaneous test results, it can be proven that the F-test results obtained a value (F- value) of 177.038 while the significance level has a significant value of $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. These results show simultaneously training, work discipline, workload, and emotional intelligence take effect significant to performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Southeast Sulawesi so that the first hypothesis proposed in this study can be accepted. Furthermore, it can be proven by the value of the coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.934, meaning that the diversity of the variables of education, work discipline, workload, and emotional intelligence on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Southeast Sulawesi can be explained by the model of 93.4 percent while the remaining 6.6 percent is explained by other variables not included in this research study. So it can be concluded that the value of the coefficient of determination (R^2) of this research model has good model accuracy because it has a value above 50 percent.

4.2.2 Training Has a Significant Positive Impact on Personnel Performance

Based on the results of testing the effect of training on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Sultra obtains an estimated coefficient of 0.315 in a positive direction, the path coefficient which is positive means that the effect of training on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Southeast Sulawesi is unidirectional. Apart from that it can be seen from the significant value of t of $0.00 < \alpha = 0.05$. Based on these results it can be said that training positive and significant effect on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Southeast Sulawesi. Improvements that occur in training provide an increase in performance Personnel or it can also be said that the better the training, the better the

performance of personnel vice versa. So that with results the could it is said that the second hypothesis proposed in this study can be accepted.

4.2.3 *Work Discipline Has a Significant Positive Influence on Personnel Performance*

Based on the results of testing the influence of work discipline on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Sultra obtains an estimated coefficient of 0.123 in a positive direction, the path coefficient which is positive means that the influence of work discipline on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Southeast Sulawesi is unidirectional. Apart from that it can be seen from the significant value of t of $0.039 < \alpha = 0.05$. Based on these results it can be said that work discipline positive and significant effect on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Southeast Sulawesi. The increase in work discipline provide an increase in performance Personnel or it can also be said that the better the work discipline, the better the performance of personnel vice versa. So that with results the could it is said that the third hypothesis proposed in this study can be accepted.

4.2.4 *Workload Has a Significant Positive Influence on Personnel Performance*

Based on the results of testing the effect of workload on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Sultra obtains an estimated coefficient of -0.120 in a negative direction, the path coefficient which is negative means that the influence of workload on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Southeast Sulawesi is not unidirectional. Apart from that it can be seen from the significant value of t of $0.037 < \alpha = 0.05$. Based on these results it can be said that the workload negative and significant effect on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Southeast Sulawesi. The increase in workload causing a decrease in performance levels Personnel. So that with results the could it is said that the fourth hypothesis proposed in this study was rejected.

4.2.5 *Emotional Intelligence Has a Significant Positive Effect on Performance*

Based on the results of testing the influence of emotional intelligence on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Sultra obtains an estimated coefficient of 0.670 in a positive direction, the path coefficient which is positive means that the influence of emotional intelligence on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Southeast Sulawesi is unidirectional. Apart from that it can be seen from the significant value of t of $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. Based on these results it can be said that emotional intelligence positive and significant effect on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Southeast Sulawesi. The increase in emotional intelligence provide an increase in performance Personnel or it can also be said that the better the emotional intelligence, the better the performance of personnel vice versa. So that with results the could it is said that the fifth hypothesis proposed in this study can be accepted.

5 Discussion

Based on objectives, gaps in research results, descriptions of research variables, hypotheses and results of data analysis, the discussion of the results of this study combines the theories and results of previous studies that can strengthen or reject the theories and results of previous studies which are described as follows:

5.1 **The Influence of Training, Work Discipline, Workload, and Emotional Intelligence on Personnel Performance**

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis, the results of simultaneous testing show that training, work discipline, workload, and emotional intelligence simultaneously have a significant effect on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Southeast Sulawesi. These results indicate that the better the training, work discipline, workload, and emotional intelligence, the better the performance The personnel has increased significantly. This means that changes in training, work discipline, workload, and emotional intelligence simultaneously have a real or significant contribution to improving service orientation, communication, emotional control, integrity, empathy, commitment to organization, initiative and cooperation which are reflections of performance. Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Southeast Sulawesi. The results of this study can confirm the consistency of the application of Police Regulation Number 2 of 2018 articles 14 and 15 and Permenpan Number 8 of 2021 that the performance measurement of police personnel consists of generic factors and specific factors. The study focused on generic performance based on Member Work Behavior (PKA). Because PKA is an assessment indicator related to predetermined performance factors and performance standards, which are applied equally to all members of the Indonesian National Police. Furthermore, research can prove the truth of the performance theory put forward by (33) performance is a comparison between actual work results and set work standards. The findings of this study indicate that the better the level of training, work discipline, workload, and emotional intelligence simultaneously will improve performance, training, work discipline, workload, and emotional intelligence are part of human resource practice, so that in improving resource practice performance good human resources are needed.

5.2 Effect of Training on Personnel Performance

The results of this study indicate that training has a positive and significant effect on performance Personnel Ditreskrim of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police. This means that the better the training then the performance Personnel Ditreskrim of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police. Changes in training improvement as reflected in the aims and objectives of the training, participants training, materials training, method training, and instructors/trainers make a very significant contribution to improving performance Personnel which is reflected in service orientation, communication, emotional control, integrity, empathy, commitment, initiative, discipline, and cooperation. The findings of this study indicate that training has a positive and significant effect on performance, meaning that the higher the training, the higher the performance. The findings of this study are consistent with the findings of research by (3), (4), (5), and (6) in their research findings showing that training has a positive and significant effect on performance, meaning that the better the level of training in an organization, the performance will increase, and vice versa if the training decreases, the performance will decrease.

5.3 The effect of Work Discipline on Personnel Performance

The results of this study indicate that work discipline has a positive and significant effect on performance Personnel Ditreskrim of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police. This means that the better the work discipline, the performance Personnel Ditreskrim of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police. Changes in increasing work discipline as reflected in *attendance, obedience, high level of vigilance, and ethical work* make a very significant contribution to improving performance Personnel which is reflected in service orientation, communication, emotional control, integrity, empathy, commitment, initiative, discipline, and cooperation. Work discipline in the organization expects employees to work in accordance with what has been set by management (preventive discipline). Discipline will be emphasized more if employees experience unexpected violations and are not in accordance with predetermined standards. Progressive discipline is a process related to worker behavior that does not meet the expected standards and is communicated in performance. The findings of this study are in line with the research of (7), (8), (9), (10) and (11) their research findings show that work discipline has a positive and significant effect on performance, meaning that the better the level of discipline of members in an organization, the better performance will be.

5.4 The Effect of Workload on Personnel Performance

The results of this study show that workload has a negative and significant effect on the performance of the Ditreskrim Personnel of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police. The results of this study indicate that the higher the workload, the lower the performance. Changes in increased workload reflected through *targets, working conditions, and work standards* will significantly reduce the level of personnel performance as reflected by service orientation, communication, emotional control, integrity, empathy, commitment to organization, initiative, discipline, and cooperation.

The findings of this study are consistent with the findings of research by (60), (61), (24) in their research findings show that workload has a negative and significant effect on performance, meaning that the higher the level of workload, the lower the level of performance, and vice versa if the workload decreases, the performance will increase.

5.5 The Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Personnel Performance

The results of this study show that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on personnel performance Ditreskrim Polda Southeast Sulawesi. This means that the better the emotional intelligence, the better the performance of personnel. Changes in increasing emotional intelligence which are reflected through the components of self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and skills in building relationships have a very significant or significant contribution to improving personnel performance which is reflected through service orientation, communication, emotional control, integrity, empathy, commitment to the organization, initiative, discipline, and cooperation. The research findings support the research findings of (23), (3), (24), (25), (26), (11), and (6) in their research findings show that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on performance, meaning that the better the level of one's emotional intelligence, the more it will improve its performance, so that emotional intelligence in an organization is needed in order to improve individual performance and in Finally, organizational performance will increase.

6 Conclusion

Based on the findings and discussion in this study, several conclusions can be put forward, namely as follows : 1). Training, work discipline, workload, and emotional intelligence simultaneously have a significant effect on performance Personnel Ditreskrim of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police. 2) Training has a positive and significant effect on

performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police . 3). Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on performance Personnel Ditreskrimsus Polda Southeast Sulawesi. The findings of this study indicate that the higher the level of discipline . 4). Workload has a negative and significant effect on personnel performance Ditreskrimsus of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police . 5). Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant impact on personnel performance Ditreskrimsus Polda Southeast Sulawesi.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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